

Cloud Quantum Computing Concept And Development

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Abstract- *In this paper, quantum circuit model using logical AND gates to measure the superposition until a range is specified. They're used to remedy complicated issues requiring powerful computation.*

Keyword- *qc, pc, comparison*

I. INTRODUCTION

A cloud quantum pc is a quantum pc that may be accessed in a cloud environment through a community. The language of quantum computing is the quantum circuit model. Massive organizations nowadays like IBM, Google Microsoft and Amazon are on pace to develop cloud quantum computer systems They combine qc with cloud computing that may be accessed by a network while not having the bodily quantum pc[1]. It way soon enough humans as a fundamental consumer could have the opportunity to test the electricity of qc systems in a cloud computing surroundings [2].

This study inspects by creating a single circuit made up of square root of NOT gates, controlled-Z gates, and a measurement. For that we are using Cirq as open source framework which allows one to write a quantum circuit model in Python. Quantum computers generally tend so that you can solve problems which have a very excessive search area. Cloud quantum computing Superposition (Hadamard Gate) - Using "QUBIT" to achieve superposition

compared to classical computing which uses bits to store their value.

Cloud-primarily based quantum computing gives direct get right of entry to emulators, simulators, and quantum processors. One of the largest advantages of availing quantum services in the cloud is that it lets in getting entry to quantum bodily-powered computers via the web. The test is to check and compare the performances of different cloud quantum computing offerings and make a contrast out of it. From the result, we can see that the quantity of qubit in line with backend and shots in step with running pretty plenty affect the execution time of a cloud quantum computing. This check will deliver the users a few perceptions and permit them to determine which cloud quantum computing services supply higher performance or faster execution time based on the specification every cloud quantum laptop offers.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

On this, organizations like IBM, Google, Microsoft, and Amazon are tempo to broaden cloud quantum computers. They integrate quantum computers with cloud computing that may be accessed by way of a network without having the bodily quantum computer [3]. There might be a comparison among each cloud quantum computing carrier primarily based on their performances, amplitudes, instances, and architecture. Especially we will be accomplishing the studies on IBM and Qutech cloud quantum computing era. The basic principle at the back of Cloud quantum

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computing such as **superposition** and **entanglement**. The amount of qubit per backend and shots per run pretty much affect the execution time of a cloud quantum computing. This take look will deliver the customers some perception and permit them to determine which cloud quantum computing services supply higher the overall performance or quicker execution time based totally on the specification every cloud quantum computer offers [4].

For each cloud quantum computing we will test the very basic of cloud quantum computing capabilities that is superposition a condition where a quantum computer can exist in different multiple states at once, for example the quantum computer can have a value either one or zero at the same time[5]. To do this quantum computers use what is called "QUBIT" to achieve superposition compared to classical computing which uses bits to store their value[6]

Figure 1: Bit and Qubit Illustration[6]

The state of the qubit will be zero or represented using and the state of one will be one is represented as. At first the state of the qubit will always be set to $|0\rangle$ or $|1\rangle$ to achieve superposition we will use the Hadamard Gate, it's basically map the initial qubit state from $|0\rangle$ to and from $|1\rangle$ to which from that measurement will make the result of the state to equal probability of 1 or 0 (50% resulting in 1 and 50% resulting in 0) for each test that is conducted [7]

Figure 2: Hadamard Gate Illustration

The zero and one from the visualization constitute the value of each qubit as a long way proper qubits constitute the qubits cost test.

Figure 3: The result probability Illustration

III. PROBLEM DEFINITION

Cloud-based quantum computing is the invocation of quantum emulators, simulators or processors through the cloud. Cloud system has some weakness in security, processing, backup and vicinity. Someway quantum computing illustrates a few modern answers to triumph over cloud weak points. Most researchers are positive about quantum computing that it will enhance cloud systems. Quantum computer systems are especially difficult to engineer, construct and program.

As a result, they are crippled via errors in the form of modern-day noise, faults and lack of quantum coherence, which is important to their operation and but falls apart earlier than any nontrivial software has a threat to run to finishing touch. to put in attitude the importance of today's being stingy with qubit intake nowadays gate-based quantum computer systems, which use logic gates analogous to the ones forming the digital circuits found inside the pc, telephone, or pill you're studying this article on, boast a trifling 50 qubits. This is just a tiny fraction of the state-of-the-art wide variety of cutting-edge classical bits your tool has to be had to it, generally masses contemporary billions.

IV. EXPERIMENTALWORK

In this, the research is conducted using Cirq, an open source Python library for creating quantum circuit model. For that purpose it is created using square root of NOT gates, controlled-Z gates.

By such it is therefore to examine the superposition of qubits until a measurement is specified. In classical computing, bits exist in one state whereas qubit exist in orthonormal state after that it comes to a base state until a measure is described.

V. RESULT

Throughout this project, the information is checked and examined by the creation of quantum circuit model. Here a simulator is created to run the circuit repetitions in terms of 0's and 1's. After that superposition is checked using cloud.


```
In [2]: import cirq

# Pick a qubit.
qubit = cirq.GridQubit(0, 0)

# Create a circuit
circuit = cirq.Circuit(
    cirq.X(qubit)**0.5, # Square root of NOT.
    cirq.measure(qubit, key='m') # Measurement.
)
print("Circuit:")
print(circuit)

# Simulate the circuit several times.
simulator = cirq.Simulator()
result = simulator.run(circuit, repetitions=20)
print("Results:")
print(result)

Circuit:
(0, 0): ---X^0.5---M('m')---
Results:
m=1000011000110100111
```

```
In [6]: import cirq

q0, q1, q2 = cirq.LineQubit.range(3)
circuit = cirq.Circuit(
    (cirq.X ** 0.7).on_each(q0, q1, q2),
    cirq.CZ(q0, q1),
    cirq.CZ(q1, q2),
    cirq.measure(q2, key='m')
)
print(circuit)
```


VI. CONCLUSION

In this examination, the circuit turned into evolved from the actual implementation using Cirq. Choosing the right device to resolve the hassle will create a quantum algorithm.

In gate primarily based quantum computer systems this could be a small circuit. As an example to create a 32 qubit random wide variety generator, sincerely create a quantum circuit that initializes 32 qubits into superposition the usage of Hadamard gates. Then measure the qubits and the consequences would be added back into actual time application.

Classical Computing is just any other way to explain how a conventional laptop works. The paintings via a binary system, i.e, facts are saved by the use of either 1 or 0. Classical computers cannot understand any other form.

Therefore Quantum Computing, however, does not follow an “on or off” model like Classical Computing. alternatively, it can concurrently handle multiple states of records with help of two phenomena referred to as superimposition and entanglement, for that reason accelerating computing at a miles quicker price and also facilitating extra productivity in records garage.

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] Haryono Soeparno - Computer Science Department, BINUS Graduate Program - Master of Computer Science Program, Bina Nusantara University, Jakarta, Indonesia
- [2] Anzaludin Samsinga Perbanga - Information System Department, School of Information Systems Bina Nusantara University Jakarta, Indonesia
- [3] Murali P, Debroy DM, Brown KR, Martonosi M. Architecting Noisy Intermediate-Scale Trapped Ion Quantum Computers 2020:529–42.
- [4] Gyongyosi L, Bacsardi L. A survey on quantum key distribution. Infocommunications J 2019; 11:14–21.
- [5] Karalekas PJ, Tezak NA, Peterson EC, Ryan CA, Da Silva MP, Smith RS. A quantum-classical cloud platform optimized for variational hybrid algorithms. Quantum Sci Technol 2020;5:24003. [6] Morimae T, Nishimura H. Rational proofs for quantum computing. Quantum Inf Comput 2020;20:181–93.

[7] Gotarane VR, Sushant Savita Madhukar Gandhi. Quantum Computing: Future Computing. Int Res J Eng Technol 2016:0-4